

FACE MASK AND SOCIAL DISTANCING DETECTOR

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Abstract

As there is no evidence that COVID-19 is declining in many parts of the world, maintaining "distance" (also called physical distance) between indoor and outdoor people is more important than ever. Covid-19 has had a profound impact on various sectors in many countries and such an impact is causing problems for many people around the world. Python can be used to capture people and monitor social distance. Deep Learning, Tensor Flow, Keras, Open CV and YOLO V4 are used for mask recognition. It uses a computer-based approach that focuses on computer automated time-keeping to see a public safe distance twenty-four hours a day, seven days each week, to inspectors in public places, commercial centers, and various locations. The act of wearing a face mask and following away from the community can save many lives as it can reduce the spread of the virus.

Key Words: Covid-19, Deep Learning, Face Mask and Social Distancing Detection, YOLOV4, Tensor Flow, Keras, Open CV.

Introduction:

By the year 2020, COVID-19 is the most life-changing activity in the world since the beginning of the year. Severe measures to be followed to forestall the spread of Covid. Protecting ourselves from the disease by wearing a face mask and following social isolation is one of the best ways. Face mask and scrubs are a challenging task. Much attention has been given to the spread of coronavirus. Therefore, in many countries, according to the law, "No entry without a mask", a face mask is considered the first step in controlling and spreading the disease. It has become a very important issue for the safety and security purposes of COVID-19. How to get a mask will determine whether the person inside the frame is wearing a face mask or not wearing a mask. Many discoveries have been developed and implemented worldwide. Today a face mask reduces the risk of a person with the virus whether they are infected with the coronavirus or not. By wearing a mask the nose, mouth, and chin do not have a covered face. Social isolation is considered the second step in controlling the spread of infectious diseases. It means that people should keep the distance between themselves and each other, reduce contact and thus reduce the spread of the virus. In this project, we are creating a face mask discovery and social distance that can distinguish between a masked face and a mask-free face. The implementation of the algorithm used for this project is in photography, video, and live video streaming. There is an urgent need to address the spread of the virus by learning the proper rules of social isolation. Citizens have ensured safety by strict rules by checking that adequate distance and application of the mask is observed. This function discusses a lightweight system that can help prevent COVID19. We can raise awareness by explaining the use of masks and the side effects of the virus without following safety precautions. The government should charge people who do not follow the proper rules.

Figure 1: Maintaining the social distancing and wear the face mask

Overcrowding should be eliminated in public places to prevent the spread of the virus. For public gatherings, activities should be given limited permissions. Many countries have imposed fines as a rule. We need to monitor social distance in real time between two people. This should be done with a real-time monitoring system. The first thing our model will do is whether someone is wearing the right mask or not.

Another thing we do is whether the distance between the two people is acceptable or not. We do this by using in-depth reading and computer- assisted reading techniques to get a personal face. There are many technologies like AI, ML etc currently working on COVID-19 that focus on different areas of COVID-19. Our paper focuses on in-depth reading strategies.

Scope and Objectives:

The scope of this project is limited to public areas, which are usually monitored with closed-circuit television cameras, eg a bridge or a shopping mall. It is believed that the guarded area should be pedestrian, and other facilities, such as cars and animals, may not be available. Here, one has to be crowded again or in people's pools. Some visual media, such as film, television, fall outside the scope of the command. We will use data obtained from fixed monitoring cameras in real-world locations. We will continue to build on existing research in the field of vision. To improve the relief process, reduce the spread of coronavirus by civilian monitoring of:

- Maintaining a Social Level
- Wearing masks in public places.

For this reason, we are developing a program that uses an in-depth learning model to distinguish people who do not wear a mask and who do not adhere to social norms. For example, the output of the model within the face frame is shown in green and the red frames or boxes indicate that the person is wearing a mask or will not wear a mask, again, in combination with a mask. The accuracy of that prediction.

Related Works:

Part of the work related to social distance and facial recognition is briefly described in this section. To find out if people are following away from society, the Euclidean distance is calculated. The model is able to distinguish facial images, even if the face is slightly hidden from the door. The model does not have the ability to see the face of the camera, its length is greater than 6ft.

- Data were generated by a limited number of samples, due to government regulations regarding personal safety and privacy. It will not be used in various settings to support the identification of a person while wearing a mask.
- The paper uses in-depth reading methods to assess whether a person is wearing a mask or not. It involves the division of three categories, namely, a person wearing a mask, or a mask that does not wear at all or does not wear a mask, has been found. The mask will work, with photos and live video streaming. It is used for at the complexity of the structure, and gives you instant results, and you can, therefore, it can be used on Camera. Restrictions include limited data availability. Paper was used as a way to properly separate facial images.
- In this paper, it is proposed that there should be a system that can limit the spread of COVID-19, as well as people who do not wear a mask, in a smart city, where public places are monitored by CCTV cameras. If a problem or confusion is found, that is, the officer will be notified, using the network. An in-depth learning framework based on the YOLO V4, trained in a database composed of images of people using and using the mask, which are collected from various sources. The most important architectural training achieved 98.7% accuracy in unseen test data. It is a system that stops when it is experiencing difficulties, the separation of the face is covered with one hand, because it looks like this person is wearing a mask.
- In the proposed model, YOLOv4 is installed and based on the framework, as well as the opposite view, the identification of people in the appropriate area of social isolation, and monitoring of adverse conditions, including people of partial appearance, and lighting variations at different times of the day. they are able to identify high- risk areas with high viral load, and infection increases. Excessive installation can be a problem with such a model. There is no way or process in place to deal with the possibility data breach.
- In a mixed-depth model, the old machine learning of facial detection. The data contains a mask and without a mask, with pictures. It uses Open CV to do that by getting real-time face-off in live streaming, and with the help of a website

Data Set:

Two databases were used to test the current method. Database 1 [16] contains 1376 photographs of which 690 photographs of people wearing face masks and another 686 photographs of non-masked people. Fig. 1 usually consists of the shape of the front face with one face on the frame and with the same type of white mask only.

Figure 2: With Mask

Figure 3: Without Mask

Database 2 from Kaggle [17] contains 853 images and its face is highlighted with or without a mask. In the picture. 2 other face masks, head turns and tilt with multiple faces on the frame and different types of masks with different colors as well.

Libraries for Proposed System:

1. Tensor Flow:

It is an open source end-to-end source. Tensor Flow is a hallmark of a mathematical library. Tensor Flow is based on a data flow and a diversified system. Tensor Flow has a large focus on training data set. This is automated image caption software Tensor Flow is a (google- created) framework. Tensor Flow was originally developed to calculate large numbers in Deep Learning. Deep Learning is a category of machine learning algorithms that use a multi-horizontal neural network. Machine Learning has helped us to build complex applications with greater accuracy. Tensor Flow is also used to resize image data in data processing.

Figure 4: Individual steps for COVID-19 face mask detector with the Tensor Flow, Keras

2. Keras:

Keras is a state-of-the-art, in-depth learning API developed by Google to utilize emotional networks. It is written in Python and is used to facilitate the implementation of neural networks. It also supports multiple backend neural network computation. All layers applied to the CNN model are applied using cameras .It also trains neural network models in a few lines of code.

3. Open CV:

Open CV is an open source computer database used to identify Open Source and can track camera actions. Face detection usually uses classification algorithms that determine whether the face is or not in a particular image. It provides values such as two divisions namely, 0 or 1. We train face mask with Tensor flow and cameras.

Figure 5: Social Distancing Detector Steps

Proposed System:

1. Yolov4:

The Yolo algorithm stands for You Only Look Once, this algorithm is a state of the art, which works in real-time system, builds on deep learning to solve various Obstetric Problems and Object Troubleshooting problems. Architecture, this is an open-neural source network where the framework is built with the help of C & CUDA, this framework includes YOLO object acquisition and object tracking. In addition, the architecture consists of a flat layer that is highly connected and a convolutional layer that is also highly connected to pass through data from each node to other nodes in the build. This transfer is in the output sequence that gives the values of 4 parts, those 4 parts defining the predicted value of the binding box, denoted by x, y, w, h, and the acquisition score and the probability class. The YOLO is part of the One-Shot family's precision and speed

detector, and there is also a Shot detector. Two-Shot object receivers are R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, and Faster R-CNN. These algorithms are accurate for getting results based on specific usage conditions but are slower compared to Yolo's, You Only Look Once is an image viewing algorithm.

Figure 6: YOLOV4 Architecture

A single neural network is used to connect different parts of an object. It takes features from the image to predict each bounding box. Discovery in the model as a retraction problem when the image is separated by $S \times S$ grids. The authors set the S value as 7. This can be changed to the YOLO configuration file. Each grid predicts the bounding boxes (B), their confidence points, and their class opportunities (C). These predictions are coded as $S \times S \times (B * 5 + C)$. Each combination box has 5 predictions: (x, y, w, h) and confidence. Each cell grid predicts class conditions with conditions (C) such as $P(\text{Class} | \text{Item})$. The properties of this Convolutional Neural Network are enhanced by the Goog Le Net model used for image classification. Like Goog Le Net their model was implemented using 24 convolutional layers that help extract features in the image followed by 2 layers that are fully integrated to predict output opportunities and links. They also came up with a faster version of YOLO called Fast YOLO using CNN with smaller layers (9 instead of 24) and smaller filters for those layers. Other than that, the training and testing parameters were similar between YOLO and Fast YOLO. Development of Mask Discovery and Discrimination Disorders using Convolutional Neural Networks.

Conclusion:

In this project we have made a brief introduction about social isolation and face mask which are important resources in the current situation. As there are many strategies for finding social distance and face masks, we use in-depth learning models. By using this method, we can achieve high accuracy. In this project, we propose a method that uses in-depth learning strategies to employ human activity, ensuring the safety of people in public places. As technology flourishes in emerging trends, the discovery of new face masks can have an impact on public health care. We also discussed in detail the social distance monitoring that helps maintain a safe environment in the post-COVID world. In addition, the proposed method makes it possible for you to get the latest performance of the data set, as well as external and external filters, and more. By getting masks we can see that a person is wearing a face mask, and giving them the opportunity to do so, and that can be very helpful to the community. This solution has the potential to significantly reduce the incidence of real world events. We believe this will help increase public safety.

Future Scope:

The future work of this study will be based on using the most effective models that can predict the improperly worn mask. The advanced system faces the difficulty of separating the face that covers their face with hands or an improperly worn mask. Big data can be used as a big dataset helps in better model training. Data sets contain a large number of records suitable for statistical analysis. The system can also be integrated into an application that can be used to monitor public places.

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